

Article Information

Submitted: September 26, 2024

Approved: November 05, 2024

Published: November 06, 2024

How to cite this article: Rashid M. The Intersection of Artificial Intelligence in Public Health and Personalized Cancer Therapy. *IgMin Res.* November 06, 2024; 2(11): 922-925. IgMin ID: igmin268; DOI: 10.61927/igmin268; Available at: igmin.link/p268

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Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI); COVID-19; Personalized medicine; Cancer; Antioxidants; Healthcare; Genetic markers

Editorial

The Intersection of Artificial Intelligence in Public Health and Personalized Cancer Therapy

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Editorial

This editorial aims to highlight the critical intersections of patient care and technology, as illustrated in our recent article collection and addresses urgent challenges posed by global health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic while exploring broader themes such as personalized medicine, ethical practices, and the nutritional impacts on health. This diverse range of research highlights the necessity of interdisciplinary approaches to address the complexities of modern healthcare.

Mario, et al. explored how high public debt affects a country's capacity to manage healthcare expenditures and fatality rates during global emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic [1]. The study reveals that high public debt severely undermines healthcare and socioeconomic systems, rendering them more susceptible to crises. Statistical analysis indicates that rising public debt correlates with declining health expenditures over time, which heightens the risk and vulnerability rate of countries, particularly Europe. Notably, a 1% increase in healthcare spending per capita is linked to a 1.2% decrease in COVID-19 fatality rates. These findings emphasize the necessity of reducing public debt through effective governance and robust institutions while safeguarding resources for healthcare. Several lines of evidence have shown that Artificial Intelligence (AI) models show good prediction performance for COVID-19 hospitalization and mortality [2], particularly in helping to effectively detect and forecast COVID-19 [3].

Additionally, AI can potentially help predict mortality, detect, screen, and trace patients, analyze health data, prioritize high-risk patients, and allocate hospital resources during pandemics [4]; particularly in areas like data quality and diversity limitations [5]; leading to better scale-up,

timely response, and reliable, efficient outcomes, sometimes outperforming humans in certain healthcare tasks [6,7] and can effectively detect clusters of COVID-19 cases and predict future outbreaks, aiding healthcare organizations in real-time disease management and vaccine development [8]. Imad, et al. reported that AI has the potential to enhance patient outcomes, lower costs, and boost efficiency [9], while also acknowledging ethical challenges like data privacy and algorithmic bias. Qazi, et al. reported that the application of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for classifying pneumonia and COVID-19 using chest X-ray images, showed that CNNs alone achieve a remarkable recall rate of 99.47% for pneumonia detection and an accuracy of 95.45% for distinguishing COVID-19 cases [10]. In addition to the COVID-19 disease, the editorial has covered other diseases like non-cardioembolic ischemic stroke and cancer as well. Studies have shown that Cardioembolic stroke is the most common subtype of stroke in COVID-19 patients, making it an uncommon manifestation in our centers [11], particularly recovered COVID-19 patients have a higher risk of ischemic stroke compared to the general population within 9 months of the infection [12] and have worse outcomes, with nearly fourfold increased mortality, half the odds of mRS scores 0-2, and one-third the odds of home discharge [13,14]. Anastasia, et al. have reported that aspirin resistance and its links to genetic markers and clinical parameters in patients with non-cardioembolic ischemic stroke by using a machine learning model which underscores the importance of combining genetic and clinical data for personalized prevention strategies [15], other studies have shown that aspirin-treated coronary artery disease patients, laboratory aspirin resistance predicts death and target vessel revascularization and is associated with stroke recurrence [16].

Furthermore, this editorial covered recent studies about different cancers like Darya Sitovskaya, et al. investigated the histological features of the stroma in high-grade gliomas, particularly focusing on isocitrate dehydrogenase 1 (IDH1) gene mutations. Their study highlights differences in collagen synthesis and stromal changes between IDH-mutant astrocytomas and IDH-wildtype glioblastomas, which may complicate treatment efforts [17]. Other studies have reported that IDH1 mutation status is more important for overall survival than histological diagnosis in high-grade astrocytic gliomas, with younger patients having more IDH1 mutations [18] and histological grading and molecular profiling are crucial for prognostic stratification of IDH-wildtype grade II gliomas, with caution when comparing them to molecular glioblastomas [19].

Ionuț, et al. addressed the challenges of diagnosing pancreatic tumors, highlighting the limitations of current imaging techniques and underscoring the importance of developing new diagnostic procedures and biomarkers to facilitate earlier detection and improve patient outcomes [20]. Other studies have explored that early detection of pancreatic cancer is crucial, and current imaging techniques, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) with Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), Immuno- Positron Emission Tomography (PET), dual-energy- Computed Tomography (CT), offers a non-invasive detection and help make optimal treatment decisions [21] particularly staging of pancreatic carcinoma [22]. Furthermore, Andrea, et al. presented a case report on a patient with epithelial ovarian cancer, advocating for the integration of Hyperthermic Intraperitoneal Chemotherapy (HIPEC) into treatment regimens. The findings suggest that HIPEC may improve patient outcomes when combined with cytoreductive surgery [23]. Other reports have shown that HIPEC combined with cytoreductive surgery prolongs overall survival and progression-free survival in advanced epithelial ovarian cancer patients [24] especially improving recurrence-free survival and overall survival in stage III epithelial ovarian cancer patients without increasing side effects [25]. Fabrizio, et al. explored strategies to mitigate rectal toxicity in prostate cancer patients undergoing radiotherapy and suggests that a fiber-/fat-free diet combined with activated charcoal and macrogol may reduce toxicity [26]. Additionally, other reports have demonstrated that a low FODMAP diet significantly decreased rectal gas and rectal volume during prostate cancer radiotherapy, with excellent patient compliance and contentment [27], and tuning constraints to individual patient characteristics and effectively reduced rectal morbidity in prostate cancer radiotherapy improving their quality of life [28]. Zaira, et al. highlighted the critical issue of breast cancer, emphasizing the importance of early detection and the role of multidisciplinary teams (MDTs) in providing comprehensive

care [29]. Other reports have shown that MDTs involving specialists in imaging, pathology, molecular diagnostics, and therapeutics for cancer care improve patient outcomes and decision-making, leading to better survival rates and enhanced cancer management [30], particularly increasing staging completion, encouraging neo-adjuvant treatment, and creating a positive work environment for team members [31] is crucial for optimal patient care and outcomes in early-stage breast cancer [32], not only breast cancer but also, other cancer like lung, colorectal, prostate cancer [33], but long-term clinical effects require further evaluation.

Amal, et al. have reported the antidepressant and antioxidant potential of protein extracts from beans and eggs, focusing on both denatured and non-denatured forms by using mouse models [34]. Significant antidepressant effects were noted, particularly at 80% saturation. Studies have shown that antidepressants may cause, promote, or inhibit cancers, with amitriptyline showing a transient positive association with liver cancer and pancreatic cancer, and others potentially increasing breast cancer risk [35], decreasing the incidence risk of ovarian cancer [36], Antidepressants with anti-tumor effects, such as Tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs), and Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors (MAOIs), show potential in treating glioblastoma by reducing adverse effects from chemo-radiotherapy and synergizing with chemotherapy [37]. Antioxidant therapy targeting oxidative stress in cancer treatment shows potential, particularly in targeting reactive oxygen species scavengers, which increase cancer cells' antioxidant capacity [38]. Therefore, understanding their mechanisms and targeting tumor cells' antioxidant capacity may have a positive therapeutic impact by modulating oxidative stress levels, which may potentially prevent tumor development and improve anticancer therapy responses.

In conclusion, the studies discussed in this editorial underscore the critical importance of collaboration across various research disciplines, particularly in areas like personalized medicine, artificial intelligence, and ethical healthcare practices. Future research should continue to investigate emerging therapies, such as antioxidant treatments while prioritizing data privacy and AI ethics through interdisciplinary approaches and the management of global health crises. This will ultimately contribute to building a more resilient healthcare system for future generations.

The perspective of using AI-based big data models can help clinicians understand tumors and develop targeted treatment strategies [39] with the integration of genomic data and drug-response data [40,41]; and improve clinical validation, which potentially leads to practice-changing cancer therapy [42] and enhance cancer diagnosis and treatment by enhancing early detection, diagnosis, classification, grading, and personalized

treatment [43]. One example is in using AI-based models in brain tumor imaging, accelerating the shift towards patient-tailored medicine, and improving diagnostics, therapeutic options, and surgical planning [44].

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How to cite this article: Rashid M. The Intersection of Artificial Intelligence in Public Health and Personalized Cancer Therapy. *IgMin Res*. November 06, 2024; 2(11): 922-925. IgMin ID: igmin268; DOI: 10.61927/igmin268; Available at: igmin.link/p268

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Organized by: IgMin Publications Inc.

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